

PHOTOCHEMICAL REDUCTIONS WITH SOME INORGANIC COLLOIDS AS ACTIVE AGENTS UNDER THE INFLUENCE OF LIGHT IN VARIOUS STATES OF POLARISATION. PART VII. PHOTOCHEMICAL REDUCTION OF URANIC ACID SOL BY SODIUM TARTRATE.

By J. C. GHOSH, T. BANERJEE AND J. C. BOSE.

In this part the characteristic features of uranic acid sol as a photochemical oxidant have been described.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Preparation of Uranic Acid Sol.—A clear golden yellow coloured sol was obtained according to the method of Szilard (*J. chim. phys.*, 1907, 5, 488, 636).

Estimation of Uranic Acid Sol prepared.—The uranium content of the sol was estimated as U_3O_8 (Treadwell and Hall, "Analytical Chemistry" 1924, Part II, p 107).

Experimental Procedure.—No reduction was observed on exposing solution of uranic acid sol alone to ultraviolet rays (366 $\mu\mu$ and 336 $\mu\mu$).

The photoreduction in presence of sodium tartrate has been estimated by titrating potentiometrically with a solution of potassium dichromate (Ewing and Eldridge *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 44, 1484). When a solution of potassium dichromate is gradually added to uranous salt, the E. M. F. of the system, measured against a calomel electrode, increases and at the null point (*i.e.*, when all the uranous salt has been converted into uranyl), a sudden rise of E. M. F. takes place under suitable experimental conditions.

As the uranous salt is very easily oxidised by the oxygen of the atmosphere, a layer of liquid paraffin was spread over it; and more over, the titrations were done in an atmosphere of carbon dioxide.

Several blank determinations of uranous salt in this laboratory by the potentiometric method gave results which were concordant within $\pm 0.2\%$. The results were further confirmed by the titration of the uranous salt with standard potassium permanganate solution.

Merck's chemically pure sodium tartrate was twice crystallised from water.

It was found that uranic acid sol does not react with sodium tartrate when kept in the dark for 10 hours.

In the following tables, d denotes the thickness of the reaction cell, I_{abs} , the intensity of radiation absorbed in ergs per sq. cm. and γ = quantum efficiency.

R E S U L T S .

Effect of Varying the Concentration of Uranic Acid Sol.

TABLE I.

$d = 0.5$ cm. Conc. of uranic acid sol = $0.017M$. Temp., 30° . Sodium tartrate = $0.333M$. $I_{\text{abs}} = 2170$. Dichromate = $0.01N$

Time.	C.c. of dichromate $\equiv 252$ c.c. reaction mixture.	$K = 2.3 \times \frac{a}{t_{\text{ec}}} \times \log \frac{a}{a-x}$
0	0.0	
120	0.35	1.23×10^{-6}
360	0.68	1.23×10^{-6}
600	0.79	1.11×10^{-6}
	Mean	1.19×10^{-6}

Similar readings were taken with other concentrations of uranic acid sol and the results are given below.

Sodium tartrate.	Uranic acid sol.	$K = 2.3 \times \frac{a}{t_{\text{ec}}} \log \frac{a}{a-x}$ (1)	γ .
$0.333M$	$0.026M$	1.17×10^{-6}	0.70
"	0.017	1.19×10^{-6}	0.72
"	0.013	1.15×10^{-6}	0.68

Effect of Varying the Concentration of Sodium Tartrate.

TABLE II.

Temp. = 30° . $I_{\text{abs}} = 2170$ ergs.

Sodium tartrate.	Uranic acid sol.	K (1).	γ .
$0.333M$	$0.026M$	1.07×10^{-6}	0.70
0.166	"	0.91×10^{-6}	0.69
0.083	"	0.73×10^{-6}	0.55

It is found that $1/K$ plotted against $1/C_{\text{tartrate}}$ gives approximately a straight line. (Fig 1).

FIG. 1.

Effect of Varying the Temperature.—Temperature coefficient $\left(\frac{K_{40^\circ}}{K_{30^\circ}}\right)$ is small being of the order of 1.1—1.2,

Effect of Varying the Intensity of Radiation Absorbed.

TABLE III.

I_{abs} .	Uranic acid sol.	Sodium tartrate.	$K(t)$.
2170	0.026M	0.166M	0.91×10^{-8}
530	"	"	0.23×10^{-8}
2170	"	0.083	0.730×10^{-8}
530	"	"	0.18×10^{-8}

It will be seen from the above table that the velocity constants vary directly as the intensity of radiation absorbed.

Quantum Efficiency of the Process.—Quantum efficiency is a little less than unity, being of the order of 0.55—0.72.

Effect of Polarised Light on the Reduction.

TABLE IV.

Nature of light.	Intensity of I_{abs} .	Uranic acid.	Sodium tartrate.	$K(t)$.
Unpolarised	2170	0.017M	0.333M	1.19×10^{-8}
d -Circularly polarised	300	"	"	0.165×10^{-8}
l -Circularly polarised	300	"	"	0.157×10^{-8}

The above table shows that on the assumption that the velocity constant varies directly as the intensity of radiation absorbed

$$V_o = V_L = V_p ,$$

V_o , V_L , V_p having the same significance as in Part II.

D I S C U S S I O N .

It will be seen from the previous tables that the velocity constants are concordant when given by the equation

$$\frac{a}{t} \log \frac{a}{a-x} \quad \dots (i)$$

This equation is obviously the integral of

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = K \frac{a-x}{a} .$$

During the process of photochemical reduction of uranic acid sol, uranic acid is formed. The active radiation is absorbed both by uranic acid and the resulting product uranous acid. It has been found experimentally that almost the whole of the incident radiation is absorbed by the reaction mixture; variation of the composition of the reaction mixture within considerable range does not affect this property. The molecular extinction coefficients of uranic acid and uranous acid in the near ultraviolet is of the same order and if "I" is the intensity of radiation absorbed by the reaction mixture, we may assume that the fraction absorbed by uranic acid is $\frac{a-x}{a} \times I$ and that by uranous acid is $\frac{x}{a} I$. Now it is the fraction of light that is absorbed by uranic acid which is photochemically active; and hence the number of excited molecules of uranic acid produced per sec.

$$= K(a-x/a) \times I/Nh\nu .$$

If C_s is the surface concentration of the tartrate on the micelle

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = K \frac{(a-x)}{a} \cdot \frac{I}{Nh\nu} \cdot C_s$$

But following Langmuir's hypothesis, we have

$C_s = \frac{K_1 C_t}{1 + K_2 C_t}$ where C_t is the bulk concentration of the tartrate in the solution.

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = K \frac{(a-x)}{a} \frac{I}{N h \nu} \cdot \frac{K_1 C_t}{1 + K_2 C_t}$$

For excess tartrate concentration, and constant intensity of radiation,

$$K = \frac{a}{t} \log \frac{a}{a-x}$$

which has been found to be case. Again K should be proportional to light intensity " I " which has also been found to be the case, the quantum efficiency being of the order of unity.

K also is proportional to $\frac{K_1 C_t}{1 + K_2 C_t}$

or $\frac{1}{K}$ is proportional to $\frac{K_2}{K_1} + \frac{1}{K_1 C_t}$ or $\frac{1}{K}$ plotted against $\frac{1}{C_t}$ should

give a straight line, which has also been found to hold good.

It will be noticed that unlike the sol tungstic acid and vanadic acid, which have greater photochemical efficiency when excited by l -circularly polarised light than by d -circularly polarised light, the photochemical efficiency of uranic acid sol when excited by equal intensities of both types of circularly polarised light is the same.